

THE AWESOME BRAIN: A BRIEF EXAMINATION OF THE NEUROCOGNITIVE DEVELOPMENTAL MILESTONES

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Introduction

In general, cognition refers to the act of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses. According to Liddell and Scott (1940), *cognition* comes from the Latin verb *cognosco*—*con* means 'with' and *gnosco* means 'know'—and is a cognate of the Greek derivative, *gi(g)nosko*, i.e., 'I know, perceive'. Franchi and Bianchini (2011) defined cognition as the ability "to conceptualize or recognize" (p.xiv). More recently, Chia and Ng (2021) have described it as the mental process that "encompasses many aspects of cognitive functions as well as processes that include attention and concentration, the concept formation of knowledge, memory, rational thinking, reasoning and logic, computation, problem solving and choice/decision making, receptive and expressive language processing that includes different levels of comprehension as well as composition of ideas and thoughts" (p.4). In short, cognition uses existing knowledge to generate new knowledge.

Neurocognition and Neurocognitive Functions

In this article, our focus is on *neurocognition*, whose prefix *neuro-* is related to nerves or the nervous system. There is a big difference between the two terms – cognition and neurocognition. The former simply refers to the process of knowing to generate new knowing: the state of being aware or informed. The latter refers to any form of cognition associated with the functioning of one or more specific cortical areas (as well as neuropathways) of the brain. These neurocognitive functions (NCFs) are cognitive functions associated with specific neuropathways or cortical networks as well as specific neuronal loci within the brain. They can be impacted by different lesions or disease processes resulting in neurocognitive malfunctioning.

The NCFs are served by the substrate of the brain's neurological matrix at both the cellular and molecular levels. Hence, it is important for counselors and allied therapists, especially when working with clients with neurocognitive challenges, to have, at least, some good understanding of neurocognition and how it is closely linked to the following two specialized areas of professional practice:

(1) **Neuropsychology:** A specialized branch of psychology that concerns how an individual's cognition and behavior are related to the brain and the rest of the nervous system; and

(2) **Cognitive Neuroscience:** The scientific study of biological processes and aspects that underlie cognition specifically focusing on neural connections in the brain that are involved in mental processes (Gazzaniga, Ivry, & Mangun, 2002).

These two disciplines broadly seek to understand how the structure and function of the brain are related to cognition and behavior, and how these can be affected by different lesions on the brain as well as brain-related diseases. Neurological research involving lesions observed in patients with brain damage relies on two key assumptions:

- (1) Brain damage can affect different aspects of cognition independently; and
- (2) A locally damaged brain functions identically to a normal brain in its "undamaged" parts.

Neurological diagnostic screening and assessment of specific NCFs can be used to deduce which areas of the brain are involved when cognitive problems are suspected. Neurocognitive dysfunction has been the center of attention in many medical conditions, which also include sleep apnea (see Sharafkhaneh & Grogan, 2015, for details). However, it is not within the scope of this article to delve into this topic.

Neurocognitive Developmental Milestones

In this article, we are interested in exploring the neurocognitive developmental milestones and how each stage can impact an individual's brain development. Nancy Guberti, a functional medicine specialist and nutritionist, has argued that "Throughout the lifetime of the human brain, it continues to undergo changes" (Guberti, 2012, para.1), and she proposed five stages of brain development according to five age-based ranges (in italic within the parentheses) beginning (i) from the time of conception through gestation; (ii) birth to 6 years old with two substages: (a) birth–2 years, and (b) 2–6 years ; (iii) 7–23 years, but we have changed it to 25 years; (iv) 26–65 years; and (v) >65 years.

We have renamed Guberti's age-based developmental stages of the brain as the developmental stages of neurocognition to reflect the following developmental milestones of NCFs (see Diagram 1):

Diagram 1. The Graph of the Neurocognitive Development Curve

Stage 1: Neurocognitive genesis (*From conception to 10 months before birth*): The fetal brain begins to develop during the third gestation week. Neural progenitor cells begin to divide and differentiate into neurons and glia. These two cell types constitute the basis of the nervous system. Neurons and connections are growing while the fetus continues to develop. These connections encode essential aspects of the unborn child's personality, behavior, cognition, and memory (Konkel, 2018).

During this stage, a pregnant mother should stay as stress-free as possible, and take folic acid, B6 & B12, to stimulate this developing fetal brain with sounds and sensations (Guberti, 2012). At all costs, the expecting mother should avoid toxins, cigarettes, heavy metals, alcohol, and drugs that will harm the fetus.

Transition from Stage 1 to Stage 2: Every infant is born with about one hundred billion brain cells. Twenty percent of them are neurons and the rest are generally made up of glial cells. As every neuron stretches in search of neighboring neurons to connect to them, they develop dendrites, axons, and dendritic spines which are required to form neural networks web. Every neuron will be connected to several neurons. As the infant captures stimulation from the environment through his or her senses, the neurons generate electrical impulses at the speed of light and passed on to other neurons in the neural web (Kandel et al., 2013).

A neuron can receive multiple signals as well as send out multiple signals. Driven by the innate calling to eat and drink, the infant grows to see patterns in the information received from the environment and begins learning to understand and interact with it to obtain food and water required by the developing body. Every experience is enhanced and built on the previous experience, and the infant makes his/her adjustment to optimize results. The needs of the infant grow as the body develops to enable him/ her to interact with the environment even more to obtain more for the growing body.

Stage 2: Neurocognitive maturity (*From birth to 6 years of age*): This second stage can be divided into the following two substages:

Substage #1: It takes place between the time of birth and 2 years of age. During that period, neuronal connectivity escalates exponentially and faster as the neural networks become extremely complex, making the brain one of the most complex organs. This has already been taking place during the stage of neurocognitive genesis. However, the

NCF process continues to develop and mature during the stage of neurocognitive maturity that can be observed during the psychosocial developmental phases of infancy, toddlerhood, and early childhood. Different parts of the brain capture and process different information: e.g., the neurons in the hippocampus connect to retain information as memory in the brain; the amygdala processes the emotions; the cerebrum is responsible for receiving and giving meaning to information from the sense organs; and the cerebellum coordinates muscle movement, balance and posture experienced by the body. As the infant continues to be exposed to the same experience and stimulations provided by the environment, the same connectivity pathway in the neural networks is reinforced further.

Substage #2: It takes place between 2 and 7 years of age. Rich experiences gained from play, arts and crafts, and social relationships established with others such as parents, siblings, and peers fundamentally shape a young child's brain development (Sriram, 2020). According to Guberti (2012), by the age of 6 years, a child's brain is at 95% of its adult weight and also peaks the energy consumption needed by the brain. Observable development during this second substage includes "Development of voluntary movement, reasoning, perception, frontal lobes active in the development of emotions, attachments, planning, working memory, and perception" (para.5). The child is also developing his/her sense of self and the life experiences also help to shape the emotional well-being (as processed by the amygdala). Guberti (2021) suggested that primary caregivers (especially the parents) need to provide their children with a nurturing environment with daily individualized communication. It is also important to take note that negative or harsh treatment or early childhood deprivation that occurs during this period may come with disturbing emotional consequences in the future, e.g., higher rates of neurodevelopmental and mental disorders in adulthood (Mackes et al., 2020).

Stage 3: Neurocognitive progression (*From 7 to 25 years of age*): According to Guberti (2012), during this stage, "The neural connections or 'grey' matter is still pruning, wiring of brain still in progress, the fatty tissues surrounding neurons or 'white' matter increase and assist with speeding up electrical impulses and stabilize connections" (para.8). The prefrontal cortex (PFC) is the last to mature and it involves the control of impulses and decision-making. The PFC is the only part of the brain that develops for a longer period (Uytun, 2018) and it is the only part of the brain that is eventually developed. It is estimated that the PFC continues to develop till the age of 25 (Uytun, 2018).

Adolescence falls within this stage of neurocognitive progression, during which a child grows to become an adult, intellectually, physically, hormonally, and socially. This is also a tumultuous transitional period with dynamic pubertal challenges and other transformations moving into adulthood that involve both gonadal and behavioral maturation (Arain et al., 2013). Several MRI studies (e.g., Casey, Jones & Hare, 2008; Giedd, 2004; Giedd et al., 1999) have found that myelinogenesis (required for proper insulation and efficient neurocybernetics) continues to develop from the childhood phase, and the cerebral region-specific neurocircuitry stays – both structurally and functionally – vulnerable to impulsive sexual activities, food consumption, and sleeping habits

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(see Arain et al., 2013, for detail). Moreover, the adolescent brain is also influenced by the genetic make-up of the individual concerned, sex hormones (e.g., estrogen, progesterone, and testosterone) that have a crucial role in myelination, and the environment (Steinberg, 2004). According to Arain et al. (2013), while the glutamatergic neurotransmission predominates, the gamma-aminobutyric acid neurotransmission remains under construction. This results in immature and impulsive behavior and neurobehavioral excitement during the adolescence period (Steinberg, 2004). Hence, adolescents must learn to regulate their reckless, irrational, and irritable behavior (e.g., substance abuse, alcohol addiction, chain-smoking, and unprotected sex).

Stage 4: Neurocognitive slowdown (*From 26 to 65 years of age*): The brain peaks its power around age 25 and lasts for 5 more years. Thereafter, the stage of neurocognitive slowdown with its downhill pattern sets in. "Last to mature and the first to go is the brain functionality of executive control occurring in the prefrontal and temporal cortices" (Guberti, 2012, para.10). Episodic memory for recalling also begins to decline. When assessed on the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale, it can be observed that the Processing Speed Index has slowed down and the Working Memory Index has also weakened, storing less information than before.

Guberti (2012) recommended that the best way to stay mentally active is to "learn new things, stay physically active, and eat a very healthy diet" (para.11).

Stage 5: Neurocognitive decline (*Beyond 65 years of age*): This fifth and last stage is known as neurocognitive decline or degeneration. Neurons are lost in the critical areas, e.g., the hippocampus (responsible for processing memories) loses its neurons or is reduced in size. Hippocampal neuron loss is a **common neuropathological feature in old age with various underlying etiologies, e.g.,** hippocampal sclerosis of aging (see Hokkanen et al., 2018).

Guberti (2012) has suggested the following ways to address neurocognitive decline: "Learn new skills, practice meditation to promote neutral emotions, exercise to improve abstract reasoning and concentration; avoid stress or incorporate stress-reducing meditation and exercises" (para.14); and eat a healthy diet with foods to nourish one's level of dopamine" (para.13-15).

Conclusion

The above neurocognitive developmental stages can be taken as a checklist, but not for formal diagnosis. They represent what a typical individual can do around a specific age, but their exact timing varies among different people.

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